

Role of Dexmedetomidine as an Anesthetic Adjuvant in Laparoscopic Surgery

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ABSTRACT

Dexmedetomidine is a highly selective α_2 agonist with properties of sedation, analgesia and anxiolysis, making it an ideal anesthetic adjuvant. Using an anesthetic adjuvant decreases the requirement of anesthetics and analgesics. We studied 60 patients of ASA grade I and II, aged between 18 to 50 years, of either gender posted for laparoscopic surgeries under general anesthesia. Patients were randomly allocated in one of the two parallel groups containing 30 patients each. Group D received Dexmedetomidine infusion at the rate of 1 mcg/kg for 20 minutes and then maintenance infusion of 0.2 mcg/kg/min till extubation. Control group NS received normal saline. Induction with propofol and fentanyl was carried out. Patients were monitored with standard monitoring. A reduction in the induction dose of propofol was observed, with a 30% less end-tidal concentration of isoflurane requirement for maintenance of anesthesia. Dexmedetomidine a highly selective alpha 2 agonist is an effective anesthetic adjuvant that can be safely used in laparoscopy.

KEY WORDS: anesthetic adjuvant, dexmedetomidine, laparoscopic surgery

INTRODUCTION:

Dexmedetomidine (Dex) has recently been added to the anesthesia armamentarium. It belongs to the class of α_2 agonists and possesses the properties of sedation, analgesia and opioid sparing effect. It differs from clonidine in being 16 times more specific for α_2 receptors.^[1] Laparoscopic surgeries under general anesthesia are associated with hemodynamic changes in the form of increased systemic vascular resistance which leads to hypertension, forcing the anesthesiologist to increase the depth of anesthesia (DOA), and at times even requires the use of vasodilators to control the rising blood pressure.^[2] Dex due to its distinct properties can be used as an anesthetic adjuvant in the form of intravenous infusion.^[3] We studied the use of Dex in laparoscopic surgeries and evaluated its effects on hemodynamics, analgesic requirement and post op recovery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

After approval of the Institutional Ethics Committee, sixty patients of age group 18-50 years belonging to American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) grade I and II; aged between 18 to 50 years; of either gender; scheduled for laparoscopic surgeries like laparoscopic cholecystectomy, laparoscopic fundoplication, total laparoscopic hysterectomy, laparoscopic appendisectomy and laparoscopic adhesiolysis, under general anesthesia were enrolled for the study. Each group consist of 30 patients. Control Group NS (N=30) and Dex Group D (N=30). Patients with ASA grade III/IV and contraindication to the use of Dex e.g. liver, renal or cardiac disorder were excluded from study. After pre-anesthetic checkup, written, valid and informed consent was taken from patients posted for laparoscopic surgery under general anesthesia. Patients were pre-medicated with tablet alprazolam 0.5 mg the night before surgery. After taking patient in OT, two intravenous (IV) lines were secured, one for routine fluids and the other exclusively for Dex. Study medication was prepared in two identical 100 ml of 0.9% saline bottles, Dex

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infusion in the concentration of 1mcg/ml.(100mcg/100ml saline) was prepared by an anesthesiologist who was blinded to the computer generated randomization schedule. The anesthetist blinded to the drug continued with the anesthesia process and recorded the study parameters. Baseline monitors like electrocardiogram (ECG), pulse oximetry, noninvasive blood pressure (NIBP) were attached. Baseline values were recorded. Patients in control group received NS infusion at the rate of 1ml/kg and continued for 20 min. After 20 min. infusion rate was changed to a maintenance infusion of 0.2 ml/kg/hr. While study group D received loading dose of Dex infusion at the rate of 1mcg/kg(1ml/kg) and continued for 20 min. After 20 minutes, the rate of Dex infusion was changed to a maintenance infusion of 0.2 mcg/kg/hr (0.2ml/kg/hr).

Patients were premeditated with glycopyrrolate 4mcg/kg, midazolam 0.03 mg/kg and ondansetron 8mg intravenously (IV). All the patients received fentanyl in dose of 2 mcg/kg IV. Anesthesia was induced with propofol 2 mg/kg IV. Succinylcholine 1.5 mg/kg was administered IV to facilitate intubation. Vasopressors response to laryngoscopy and intubation was documented by noting heart rate and blood pressure. All patients were intubated with appropriate sized cuffed endotracheal tube passed orally, and the placement was confirmed with auscultation and end-tidal carbon dioxide (EtCO₂) reading. Anesthesia was maintained with nitrous oxide and oxygen mixture (60:40), and isoflurane. Vecuronium used as non depolarizing muscle relaxant. Intraoperative anesthetic requirement was gauged by hemodynamic HR and BP. Response to pneumoperitoneum was documented and requirement of additional anesthetic/analgesic noted. Whenever required, anesthesia was deepened by increasing the concentration of inhalational anesthetic agent. Any additional requirement of metoprolol or nitroglycerine to control BP was noted. Dex infusion was continued until extubation. Hemodynamic response to extubation was documented.

Intraoperative monitoring was documented during the pre-induction, after the loading dose of Dex, at the induction of anesthesia, during laryngoscopy and intubation, and at pneumoperitoneum and then

every 15 min till the end of surgery and continued during extubation and post operatively. At the end of surgery, diclofenac sodium 75 mg was added to the IV fluid for postoperative analgesia. Any side effects like hypotension, bradycardia, respiratory depression, postoperative nausea and vomiting were noted. Patients were monitored in the recovery room, and then shifted to the ward.

Our study was prospective double blind case control study. Results are expressed as mean (Standard Deviation, SD) or median (range) unless otherwise stated. Statistics were performed using Chi Square test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to compare the characteristics, and repeated measures of ANOVA were used to assess the changes in the HR and BP. p value < 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS:

A total of sixty patients were enrolled in our study. Table 1 depicts the demographic data. Mean HR on starting was 88 ± 9.6 (19) which fell to lowest mean of 64.2 ± 9.6 (11) in study group D ($p = 0.0001$). HR was however sustained for the entire duration of infusion. Patients had sinus bradycardia (HR < 60) at the start; but none required any therapy for treatment of this bradycardia. Mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) to start with was 126 ± 10.6 , and fell to 96.6 ± 10.2 with loading dose of Dex ($p = 0.004$). After that minimal change was observed for entire duration of infusion. Similar observations were made at the time of creation of the pneumoperitoneum. The rise in HR after intubation and after pneumoperitoneum was significant. Similar changes were observed in mean systolic blood pressure during intubation and pneumoperitoneum in NS group. Mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) fell from 78 ± 6.4 to 72 ± 8.4 in Dex group which was not statistically significant. There was good control over the vasopressor response during laryngoscopy. None of the 30 patients in Dex group needed either metoprolol or nitroglycerine to counter the hypertension effect of pneumoperitoneum. While 80 % (24) patients needed propofol or metoprolol in NS group, other 20 % (6) needed both. The results were analyzed using IBM SPSS v 20.

The mean dose of propofol required for induction was 60.5mg. Intraoperative, whenever propofol was required, it was given in 10 mg top ups. We also studied the requirement of isoflurane which was adjusted to maintain stable BP. It was

Table 1: Patient's characteristics and duration of surgery (Mean \pm SD)

	Group D(n=30)	Group NS(n=30)
Age (Years)	41.4 \pm 8.12	43.7 \pm 8.56
Sex (M:F)	13:17	11:19
Weight (kg)	59.24 \pm 10.16	57.88 \pm 10.4
Duration of surgery (min)	86.32 \pm 11.26	80.15 \pm 10.42

Table 2: Changes in Mean Arterial Pressure (Mean \pm SD)

	Group D	Group NS	Statistical Significance
Preoperative	126.4 \pm 10.6	124 \pm 10.8	p>0.05; NS
After infusion	96.6 \pm 10.2	118.2 \pm 10.3	p<0.01; HS
1 min after induction	82 \pm 6.8	98 \pm 12.4	p<0.01; HS
1 min after intubation	90.2 \pm 10.2	118.6 \pm 14.12	p<0.05; S
After Pneumoperitoneum	94 \pm 10.6	128 \pm 18.11	p<0.01; HS
15 min	90 \pm 12.8	132 \pm 13.6	p<0.05; S
30 min	86 \pm 12.4	128 \pm 18.4	p<0.05; S
45 min	87 \pm 13.4	126 \pm 15.4	p<0.05; S
60 min	90 \pm 14.5	126 \pm 10.4	p<0.05; S
End of Pneumoperitoneum	84.2 \pm 12.8	120 \pm 12.6	p<0.01; HS
Postoperative period	88.6 \pm 10.12	111.14 \pm 18.26	p<0.05; S

Table 3: Changes in Heart Rate (Mean \pm SD)

	Group D	Group NS	Statistical Significance
Preoperative	88 \pm 9.6	86.2 \pm 9.2	p>0.05; NS
After infusion	72 \pm 9.2	82 \pm 10.6	p<0.05; S
1 min after induction	64.2 \pm 9.6	79.4 \pm 11.5	p<0.05; S
1 min after intubation	70.2 \pm 10.4	97.2 \pm 12.7	p<0.01; HS
After Pneumoperitoneum	74.8 \pm 9.3	96 \pm 13.8	p<0.01; HS
15 min	74 \pm 10.3	92 \pm 13.4	p<0.05; S
30 min	76 \pm 10.2	96 \pm 14.3	p<0.05; S
45 min	74 \pm 9.1	94 \pm 13.2	p<0.05; S
60 min	72 \pm 11.2	96 \pm 12.8	p<0.05; S
End of Pneumoperitoneum	72 \pm 10.4	90 \pm 10.2	p<0.05; S
Postoperative period	73.2 \pm 9.6	96.4 \pm 15.4	p<0.01; HS

S–Significant; NS –Not Significant; HS –Highly Significant

observed that the end-tidal concentration of isoflurane required was between 0.8 to 1.2 throughout the surgery, with peak requirement at the beginning immediately after intubation, and then again during creation of pneumoperitoneum.

Concentration of isoflurane as was observed to be almost 30% less with Dex.

Total fentanyl requirement after pneumoperitoneum in saline group was extubation response was studied which appeared to be smooth in

Table 4: Recovery time (min), Mean \pm SD

	Group D	Group S	Statistical Significance
Extubation time (min)	4.28 \pm 1.08	9.18 \pm 2.24	p<0.05; S
Response to verbal command (min)	6.76 \pm 1.41	10.89 \pm 2.48	p<0.05; S
Time for orientation (min)	6.93 \pm 1.60	12.42 \pm 1.21	p<0.05; S

Dex group compared to saline group. Patients showed immediate eye opening and were responsive to verbal commands indicating no residual effects of Dex. There was no difference in vecuronium requirement in both the groups. All patients were hemodynamically stable and comfortable of Dex group in the recovery room. None of patients had postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV), hypotension, bradycardia or episodes of respiratory depression and were shifted to the ward after two hours.

DISCUSSION:

Laparoscopic surgery offers intraoperative stress during pneumoperitoneum by increasing the systemic vascular resistance and blood pressure at the same time producing nociception.^[2] Dex, an imidazole compound, displays specific and selective α_2 adrenergic receptor agonism.^[4,5] The unique properties of Dex render it suitable for analgesia during the perioperative period.^[6] The major sedative and antinociceptive effects of Dex are attributable to its stimulation of α_2 A subtype located in locus coeruleus^[7]. It is the specificity of dex for α_2 receptor that makes it a more effective sedative and analgesic agent than clonidine. Dex is eight times more specific for α_2 receptors than clonidine (α_2 : α_1 ratio for dex is 1620:1 and that for clonidine is 220:1).^[17]

Dex potentiates anesthetic effects of all intraoperative anesthetics, regardless of the method of administration. The profound reduction in anesthetic requirement was shown to be mediated through central α_2 adrenergic receptors. Possible anesthetic effects also have been suggested in humans. IV and IM administration has shown to reduce requirement of thiopentone by 17% in a group that receiving low dose Dex, and up to 30% in a group receiving high dose Dex.^[8] We observed that Dex significantly reduces induction dose of propofol. Dex also decreases the requirement of inhalational agents. Routine end tidal concentration required for maintenance of anesthesia is 0.8 to 1.2%.^[3] First report of reduced requirement of

isoflurane with Dex in humans was published in 1991^[9], which showed a 25% reduction of maintenance and concentration of isoflurane in patients who received Dex. A 35-50% reduction of isoflurane requirement in patients treated with either low or high doses of isoflurane without premedication has been reported.^[10] Similar observations regarding isoflurane requirement were made in our study.

Dex has been shown to attenuate the sympathoadrenal stimulation during intubation effectively.^[11] We observed that Dex effectively attenuates the vasopressor response of laryngoscopy, and intubation and the sympathoadrenal response occurring with pneumoperitoneum. Analgesic properties have been demonstrated in studies that used Dex as a sole analgesic after minor surgeries.^[12] Opioid requirements in the intra and post-operative period are reduced by Dex. The α_2 mechanism of action is involved in modulation of nociception at the level of spinal noradrenergic systems.^[13] There is a clear evidence that α_2 receptors located in dorsal horn neurons of spinal cord might release endogenous opiate compounds.^[14] We observed that fentanyl in the dose of 1.5 mcg/kg was sufficient to provide analgesia, at least till the time of pneumoperitoneum. However, 20% of patients required fentanyl top up during pneumoperitoneum. Dex has been shown to provide good hemodynamic stability.

Dex has shown less respiratory depression than any other sedatives.^[15] Infusion can be continued safely till extubation.^[16] In our study, none of the 30 patients had episodes of respiratory depression in the post-operative period. Dex use permits lower doses of anesthetics to be used and decreases the opioid requirement, thus resulting in a more rapid recovery from anesthesia.

CONCLUSION:

Dexmedetomidine, a highly selective alpha 2 agonist, is an effective anesthetic adjuvant that can be safely used in laparoscopic surgery. We observed that

Dex is a good anesthetic adjuvant that decreases the requirement of anesthetics and opioid, attenuates sympathoadrenal response, maintains the stable hemodynamic, and provides an excellent recovery profile.

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